

Magazine

NEWSLETTER

January 2024

**FLAMINGo - Fabrication of
lightweight aluminium metal matrix
nanocomposites and validation in
green vehicles**

3rd year of Activities p.4

Future Events by Partners p.24

FLAMINGo at GACS 2023 p.12

Our first success stories p.9

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Contents

1. FLAMINGo in a nutshell.....	p.03
2. 3 rd year of Activities.....	p.04
3. Our first success stories.....	p.09
4. Our Collaborations.....	p.11
5. FLAMINGo at GACS 2023.....	p.12
6. News and Updates.....	p.14
7. Past Events by Partners.....	p.18
8. Future Events by Partners.....	p.24
9. Contact info.....	p.26

1. FLAMINGo in a nutshell

FLAMINGo

Goals

FLAMINGo's objectives encompass the production of reinforced **Aluminum Metal Matrix Nano-Composites (Al-MMnC)** featuring **enhanced strength and stiffness** compared to existing aluminum alloys in automotive applications.

The project aims to offer engineering solutions to replace steel components in **Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV) parts**, resulting in a significant reduction in weight.

Achieved Milestones

FLAMINGo has reached significant milestones, marking key advancements in the project. Brunel successfully delivered the initial cast billets designed for extrusion to Constellium, facilitating the next stages of the manufacturing process.

ÖGI, achieved a groundbreaking step with the delivery of the first die-casted electric vehicle (EV) component, showcasing the project's practical applications in automotive innovation.

Furthermore, Constellium supplied extruded Aluminum Metal Matrix Composites (Al-MMCs) to ISQ, where welding processes were carried out, demonstrating successful collaboration and progress in developing lightweight and durable automotive components.

Technologies

FLAMINGo employs cutting-edge technologies to revolutionise the production of lightweight automotive components. The project leverages **solid-state mechanical milling** to create Novel Aluminum Metal Matrix nano-Composites (Al-MMnCs), enhancing strength and stiffness and **topology optimisation** is employed to design components for optimal weight reduction. Manufacturing processes like **Low-Pressure Die Casting (LPDC)** and **Green Sand Casting (GSC)** ensure precise and efficient production, while **extrusion and welding techniques** are applied to assemble Al-MMnC components, guaranteeing robustness.

Moreover, **non-destructive techniques** are utilised for quality assurance. FLAMINGo is committed to **sustainability through recycling**, contributing to the development of eco-friendly solutions in the automotive industry.

Markets Addressed

FLAMINGo strategically addresses multiple markets, focusing on the **Lightweight Metals market**, where the demand for advanced materials is on the rise for enhanced performance and efficiency. In particular, the project targets the **Aluminium Alloys in the Automotive market**, aiming to revolutionise vehicle manufacturing by introducing innovative aluminum composites with superior properties.

Furthermore, FLAMINGo aligns with the booming **Electric Vehicles (EVs)** market, contributing to the ongoing shift towards sustainable and lightweight solutions, crucial for optimising the performance and energy efficiency of electric vehicles.

2. 3rd year of Activities

Reflecting on the past activities during the third year, MBN continued its pioneering journey in nano-additive production. Expanding upon the lessons learned from pilot-scale testing, we dedicated ourselves to refining processes and exploring avenues for improvement. Our persistent research efforts focused on broadening the scope of metal/nanoparticle systems, ensuring adaptability to a wide array of industrial applications. Throughout the third year, MBN solidified collaborations with suppliers and fine-tuned production methods, seeking the optimal balance between cost-effectiveness, scalability, and top-tier performance. Additionally, MBN maintained its commitment to sustainable practices by further investigating the in-situ formation on Titanium Carbide particles, and on pre-treatments of Silicon Carbide to improve the master yield and performances. While challenges persisted, our activities concluded with notable achievements, including the successful production and delivery of 55 kg of nano-additives, facilitating the creation of an impressive 2.3 tons of Aluminum Metal Matrix Nano-Composite. In collaboration with the partners MBN is now exploring how to improve on the masterbatch delivery method for a continuous improving on the final Aluminium-Metal Matrix Nano-composites.

ISQ is participating in several tasks of FLAMINGo project, such as the analysis of potential sources of nanomaterials release and pathways that workers may be exposed during partners' manufacturing activities. This task aims to promote a safe and sustainable-by-design use of nano-powders and nanoproducts since the early stages of the innovation process. The FLAMINGo materials formulation using nano-powders, as well as the manufacturing and processing process of the innovative nanoproducts is distributed in several pilot and industrial lines of the project partners. The innovative nanoproduct composed by aluminum metal matrix nanocomposites and produced through a combination of casting and/ or extrusion processes aims to be used for building structural components for an electric vehicle prototype. During 2023, ISQ assessed the risk of workers' exposure to nanocomposites in the green sand-casting line of the Austrian Casting Institute (ÖGI). During the March 8th - 9th FLAMINGo General meeting at the Austrian Casting Institute, ISQ delivered a training on Safety to Advanced (Nano)materials in the Workplace. This training session aimed to provide technical knowledge to FLAMINGo partners concerning the potential exposure risks associated with the use of nanomaterials in the workplace, and the procedures recommended by international bodies for their risk assessment and management (OECD, CEN, ECHA). The recent Safe-and Sustainable-by-Design strategy proposed by the European Commission was also addressed.

...of profits...
...short period, it will bankrupt the...
...available to support the bank's returns...
...Presumably, the bank's returns...
...well makes the customer who borrows...
...the 1990s, the...
...most...

2. 3rd year of Activities

In the 3rd year of FLAMINGo, ÖGI has succeeded in completing the optimisation activities for the steering knuckle with the help of mould filling and solidification simulations as well as topology optimisation. The steering knuckle was not only optimised in relation to lightweight construction but also taking castability

into account. A total of four topology-optimised and FEM-calculated variants of the steering knuckle, considering the left and right side, were simulated using the MAGMASOFT® casting process simulation. The simulation was quite accurate in predicting the defects within the components. The areas with defects predicted in the simulation were also reflected in the real components. This made it possible to correlate the simulated results with the real results. Which was crucial for validating the reliability and effectiveness of the simulation.

The castings of the steering knuckle were made using the aluminium alloy A356 (Al Si7Mg0.3) and a masterbatch containing a 1:1 ratio of copper/SiC (Al - 20Cu 20nSiC). The castings were characterised including evaluation of mechanical properties and chemical analysis. The influence of the heat treatment on Al-MMnCs castings was also analysed. In the tests performed, a higher elongation loss due to T6 hardening was observed in the samples without nanoparticles, and it was also found that the hardening effect remains temperature stable due to the introduction of nanoparticles.

Over the last year ALKE has contributed in assisting partners involved in manufacturing components for FLAMINGo. ALKE has provided guidance in decision-making processes to ensure the created parts meet the necessary standards. Additionally, ALKE has analysed feedback

regarding the performance of these parts and offered suggestions to enhance the overall manufacturing process.

In terms of technology validation, ALKE has ensured that the planned tests for verifying FLAMINGo's technology align well with the actual parts. Moreover, ALKE has already arranged the sensors in the ALKE demo vehicle, ensuring proper placement and connectivity for real-time monitoring during tests.

Dedicated to enhancing the Rear Frame Demonstrator, ALKE has focused on refining this specific FLAMINGo component. Through exploration of innovative ideas, they have sought to optimise its functionality and simplify the manufacturing process. This dedicated effort contributes to ensuring that FLAMINGo's rear frame is robust and efficient when finally assembled.

2. 3rd year of Activities

During the 3rd year, Brunel University London (BUL) mainly contributed to WPG and WP7 through a series of pilot scale (1:1) castings, with the help of Constellium partners. In these castings, TiC reinforcement nanoparticles were added to the aluminium melt. Mechanical stirring along with ultrasonic melt treatment were used to aid in introducing and dispersing the particles. The as-cast microstructures of the billets were analysed. TiC particles were identified in the castings using SEM and EDX, however it was found that the TiC particles sedimented in the melt due to the prolonged processing time. This was a challenge which was unique to the 1:1 scale, as the processing times in the lab-scale experiments were relatively shorter than the

processing times in the pilot scale experiments. Subsequently, lab-trials to determine the sedimentation rate of the TiC particles were carried out and this information was used to refine the 1:1 scale process. In the most recent pilot scale castings, a longer stirring device was used to reach a greater depth in the crucible, so that the particles residing at the bottom of the crucible can be dispersed in the melt. In addition to this, the melt volume was reduced to 70-80kg in order to achieve a shorter casting time. Shorter casting time means less time for the particles to sediment. The 1:1 scale casting process continues to be refined and improvements are made with each casting trial. The billets from the pilot scale experiments were extruded by Constellium and were subsequently sent to BUL for characterisation including hardness testing and microstructure examination. It was found that the extrusion process broke up particle agglomerates and aided in the dispersion of the particles. BUL also contributed towards WP5 through High Pressure Die Casting (HPDC) Al-MMC with TiC reinforcement. Upon characterisation of the microstructure, TiC were identified in the castings. Mechanical testing was carried out and the addition of TiC resulted in a 5% increase in the Yield Strength. Furthermore, BUL contributed towards WP4 with basic CFD simulations showing the effectiveness of stirring impellers with different geometries.

In the 3rd year of the FLAMINGo project, Constellium (CSTM) has primarily worked on the main work package (WPG) – extrusion production methods, and also contributed to other work packages, such as Topology Optimisation & Process Simulation (WP4) and Evaluation & Characterisation (WP7).

For WPG, Constellium continued to support the Brunel team on upscaling from lab-scale to 1:1 scale DC casting and optimising the Al-MMnC casting recipe. We also took the opportunity to identify some challenges during the upscaling process (e.g. sedimentation of nanoparticles into bottom of crucible at 1:1 Scale DC-casting), which have been confirmed through a fire assay and a lab-scale experiment. Another finding was that the position

of the impeller/degasser with respect to the crucible bottom and treatment time may be influential to keep nanoparticles suspended on the melt longer. These findings will be used as inputs for the next 1:1 Scale Al-MMnC DC-casting trials along with utilising the new degasser equipment with better reach towards bottom of crucible to achieve better dispersion of the nanoparticles in the melt. Concerning the main task (Task 6.2: Extrusion of Al-MMnC), Constellium continued to perform extrusions of the preliminary 1:1 Scale Al-MMnC DC-cast billets into different extrusion geometries (i.e. bumper beam and flat strips), as well as optimised the processing recipes in order to maximise the mechanical properties of Al-MMnC material. We also extruded some parts from base materials for ALKE as a pathfinder for manufacturing route for the main demonstrator. Additionally, we also provided ISQ with samples for Al-MMnC welding assessment.

In relation to WP4, Constellium proposed a more optimised part design to further lightweight the main demonstrator (rear-frame of the ALKE EV), produced the corresponding extrusion dies, and has been working on optimising the extrusion recipe for those dies.

For WP7, Constellium carried out an evaluation of the mechanical properties of the produced Al-MMnC extruded parts. Furthermore, we also confirmed that there are no detrimental effects of the extrusion process in relation of Nanoparticles strengthening in the alloy through an evaluation of the mechanical properties of the preliminary Al-MMnC 1:1 Scale DC-Cast billets, both at as-cast and heat-treated state.

2. 3rd year of Activities

Group Kampakas is responsible for Task 8.3 of WP8, related to the recycling activities of the FLAMINGo project. During the 3rd year of the project, Kampakas carried out recycling of Al-MMnC masterbatches reinforced with SiC NPs, delivered by ÖGI. A certain procedure was established for the recycling process of the masterbatches, including preparation of the charged material, followed by melting and pouring. The NPs were removed by applying specific treatments, including fluxing for deoxidation of the melt and degassing for NPs removal, that was later confirmed by

hardness tests. Moreover, samples of dross collected at different stages of the recycling process were sent to MBN for analyses. Following the recycling of masterbatches containing SiC NPs by ÖGI, Kampakas is going to carry out recycling of masterbatches with TiC NPs, delivered by Constellium. During the 3rd year of the project, Kampakas also participated in activities of WP9 and more specifically Task 9.6, that is led by EWF, conducting a training session focusing on Al-recycling.

Global Factor has focused its latest efforts on detailing the information required to continue the life cycle analysis and life cycle cost analysis study. It is necessary to understand and schematise as much as possible all the processes that take place in the manufacturing of the different components of the electric vehicle in order to obtain accurate results. With that assumption, the required data collection sheets have been extended to the partners, a briefing has been given for the collection of the final round of data, and data collection is currently being planned to streamline the whole calculation process once all the necessary data is available. On the other hand, thanks to this level of detail, the 1st draft of the calculation tool has been produced, and the bibliographic information required in the process can be expanded in the coming weeks. Synergies have also been detected with the possible results of the Health and Safety section, which will probably allow addressing some of the conclusions together with the environmental impact reflected by the life cycle analysis.

EWF has supported the realisation of different training activities in a wide range of topics. Several training sessions have been organised in topics such as additive production, nanomaterial safety, aluminium extrusion and more recently, innovation management, life-cycle assessment (LCA) and recyclability of aluminium alloys. Following these sessions, physical workshops will be organised to demonstrate the results from FLAMINGo.

In what regards standardisation, a validation of the standards identified within the scope of the activities carried out in FLAMINGo is being carried out together with external stakeholders, in order to ensure the industrial implementation of the developments generated along the project.

2. 3rd year of Activities

AXIA as leader of WPS, is responsible for building the Exploitation and Dissemination strategy of the project. Their focus is on formulating tailored business plans and strategies to facilitate the effective market adoption of partners' outcomes. In the project's third year, AXIA updated the customised business plans for FLAMINGo's industrial and commercial partners, along with exploitation plans for research institutions. They presented an Exploitation and IPR seminar to the consortium highlighting pivotal strategies for leveraging project outcomes. Intellectual Property management, including a 1st patent landscape analysis and an updated plan for IP protection, was undertaken. AXIA conducted a detailed competition analysis following a Porter's 5 forces methodology, developing strategic plans for the successful commercialisation of their outcomes.

In terms of dissemination, AXIA collaborates with EXELISIS on monitoring and supporting clustering activities, event participation, and the creation of visual and printed materials. In particular, AXIA actively participated in a Global Automotive Components and Suppliers Expo 2023, where they represented FLAMINGo in the Enlight EVs booth, along with other partners, and also presented FLAMINGo in a clustering event.

During the 3rd year of the FLAMINGo project, EXELISIS actively advanced dissemination and communication efforts, including the successful launch of the project's yearly newsletter (Issue #2) and their participation in the organisation committee for the Enlight EVs participation

in the Global Automotive Components and Suppliers Expo 2023. This event is a leading event in the field of the automotives, and EXELISIS was responsible for the design of the booth where FLAMINGo participated along with other projects.

EXELISIS is also managing FLAMINGo's online presence across various platforms, including the official website, LinkedIn, Facebook and Twitter. Moreover, over this period EXELISIS updated the data management plan, by collecting any additional data generating procedures from the consortium. Finally, EXELISIS supported AXIA in various tasks related to market and competition analysis, contributing significantly to the project's overall success in both dissemination and exploitation domains.

3. Our first success stories

I Preliminary results

FLAMINGo has rigorously evaluated the Aluminum Metal Matrix Composites (Al MMnCs) produced through Low-Pressure Die Casting (LPDC), Green Sand Casting (GSC), and extrusion techniques. The testing process focused on key mechanical properties, including ultimate tensile strength, yield strength, elongation, and modulus of elasticity. These tests provide crucial insights into the structural integrity, strength, and flexibility of the Al MMnC components, ensuring that they meet and exceed industry standards for performance and reliability. The outcomes of these assessments play a pivotal role in validating the effectiveness of FLAMINGo's innovative manufacturing approaches in delivering lightweight yet robust solutions for the automotive sector. Table I summarises some of the results.

AL-MMNC	ALLOY/ MASTERBATCH	YS (MPA)	UTS (MPA)	EL (%)	E (GPA)
LPDC & GREEN SAND CASTING	3XX SERIES +T6	+10 TO +30%	+12 TO +35%	~	-
EXTRUSION	6XXX SERIE	+8 TO +20%	+10%	-30%	+6%

Table I: Preliminary results of mechanical properties of Al MMnCs

Topology optimised steering knuckle

A [teaser video](#) was shared to represent the FLAMINGo new aluminium nanocomposites automotive component optimised through topology optimisation. Through topology optimisation a reduction of weight and the improvement of structural stiffness is achieved. The specific part under development in this case was a steering knuckle. A steering knuckle is a crucial component of a vehicle's suspension system. It is a part of the front wheel assembly and connects the wheel to the suspension and steering components. The ultimate design of the component, when compared to a market steel component, resulted in an overall reduction of approximately 30%, accompanied by enhanced performance and significant energy and cost savings.

Topology optimised component led by ÖGI

Extrusion process led by Constellium

3. Our first success stories

Extrusion process successfully concluded at Constellium facilities

The extrusion process at Constellium facilities involves the manufacturing of Al-MMC specimens and parts which are then evaluated for the homogeneity, as well as their processing time and costs. Extrusion has been consistently regarded by car manufacturers as a method suitable for extensive use in crafting the Body in White (BIW) of a car over the years, as a cost-effective and budget-friendly technology. Following to the extrusion process, quenching of the components was also investigated. Quenching is a rapid cooling process that helps to set the desired properties in the extruded aluminum components. This combination of extrusion and quenching is crucial for shaping the aluminum into the required forms while ensuring that the resulting components possess the desired mechanical and structural characteristics. In [this video](#) short footage from the Constellium facilities is presented while both techniques are applied.

Extrusion process
after quenching

Constellium

4. Our Collaborations

Enlight EVs Cluster

The FLAMINGo project is continuing its efforts in joining forces with the Enlight EVs cluster of projects funded under the same "LC-GV-06-2020 - Advanced light materials and their production processes for automotive application" topic. The cluster is formed by **LEVIS**, **REVOLUTION**, **Fatigue4light**, and **ALMA** projects with a common goal; to advance innovations and technologies in the field of lightweight materials for various applications, aiming to foster sustainability, efficiency, and excellence in strategic industries. This alliance supports the organisation of common activities, such as workshop, webinars and conferences, while it also opens discussions in the field of lightweight vehicles and sustainable mobility.

Topic: **LC-GV-06-2020 - Advanced light materials and their production processes for automotive application**

The FLAMINGo project recently connected with the SALIENT EU Project. SALIENT is an EU-funded project that focuses on developing resilient light vehicle designs. These designs prioritise enhanced compatibility with mixed traffic scenarios and improved crash and collision performance. The project aims at a more circular, lightweight, safe and smart vehicle compared to available solutions on the market today. EXELISIS, partner of FLAMINGo, is in communication with the SALIENT project representatives while we have been invited in initiatives, including the ELCA workshop and podcast organised with the occasion of the Global Automotive Components and Suppliers Expo in Stuttgart, on 5 December 2023. Project website: <https://www.salient-project.eu/>

Through the SALIENT project FLAMINGo was introduced to the ELCA initiative. ELCA (European Lightweight Cluster Alliance) is a cooperative venture with the objective of expediting the integration of lightweight materials in key industries. While the primary emphasis is on mobility, the alliance extends its scope to encompass other sectors related to lightweighting, such as energy, healthcare, defence, and construction. This collaborative effort is geared toward translating lightweight technologies into practical applications and exploring market opportunities. Project website: <https://elcanetwork.eu/>

5. FLAMINGo at GACS 2023

GACS 2023

05 - 07.12.23 Stuttgart, Germany

The Enlight EVs cluster actively participated in the Global Automotive Components and Suppliers Expo 2023 (GACS) held in Stuttgart, Germany, from December 5th to 7th, 2023. The ALMA, LEVIS, FLAMINGo, and Revolution projects presented their outcomes during a dedicated event organised by the cluster, enhancing awareness of lightweighting electric vehicle components. The projects showcased demos at the booth during the 3-day exhibition, contributing to the exposition's focus on cutting-edge global manufacturing expertise in the automotive industry.

Enlight EV Cluster event

On December 5th, alongside the GACS Expo, the Enlight EV Cluster organised a conference at the International Congress Center, featuring over 50 registered participants. Salima Abu Jeriban, Project Adviser for Clean Road Transport at the European, Climate, Infrastructure & Environment Executive Agency CINEA, opened the conference, providing informative introductions to each project. The EnlightEVs cluster brings together EU-funded R&D projects, aiming to develop innovative and sustainable solutions for reducing EV weight. The cluster, consisting of ALMA, LEVIS, Fatigue4Light, FLAMINGo, and Revolution projects, collaboratively presented insights and advancements in lightweighting technologies.

Greenvehicles Levis, ALMA, Revolution, and FLAMINGo each had dedicated presentations. Levis discussed circular lightweight EV component innovations, ALMA focused on sustainable lightweighting, Revolution explored the digitalisation of lightweight EV components, and FLAMINGo highlighted its goal of strengthening aluminum for automotive components' lightweighting. Mr Vasilis Maris, project Manager from AXIA Innovation gave insights on the FLAMINGo project. With the conference concluding, Salima congratulated the projects for promoting knowledge and technology transfer.

5. FLAMINGo at GACS 2023

Enlight EVs Booth

Simultaneously, the Enlight EVs cluster shared a booth at the Global Automotive Components and Suppliers Expo, drawing significant interest from visitors, especially from the automotive and component manufacturing sectors. Representatives engaged in discussions with Toyota, BYD, and Ford Motor Company, addressing inquiries on sustainability, recycled materials, lightweight components, and electric vehicle battery life improvements.

Insights from the FLAMINGo project revealed positive engagement at the booth, with interest in topology optimisation, design, and die casting for achieving lightweighting.

Mr Vasilis Maris from AXIA Innovation expressed gratitude for the opportunity, emphasising the project's focus on reducing vehicle weight, enhancing battery life, and engine performance for sustainable vehicles. Thomas Pabel from ÖGI outlined the next steps, involving casting prototypes of steering knuckles for testing and integration into ALKE trucks.

The conference and expo successfully facilitated collaboration, knowledge sharing, and networking among industry stakeholders, reinforcing the commitment of the projects to innovation and sustainability in the automotive sector.

[Find more about GACS EXPO 2023 in our Press Release here!](#)

i. Focus on topology optimisation without SiC-NP, ii. Focus on castability in green sand casting, iii. Focus on castability in LPDC reinforced with nSiC-NP, iv. 3D-printed model, focus on max topology optimisation.

Aluminium-SiC & Aluminium-TiC Additive for Metal Matrix Nanocomposite.

Extruded parts developed by Constellium.

6. News and Updates

MBN at ALKE facilities

During December 2022, MBN had the opportunity to visit the facilities of Alke Electric Vehicles as part of the ongoing collaboration within the H2020 FLAMINGo Project. This visit was a significant step in fostering the partnership between MBN and Alke Electric Vehicles, providing an insightful exploration of the project's developments and innovations. The engagement aimed to strengthen the knowledge exchange and synergies between the project partners, contributing to the shared goals of advancing lightweight and sustainable solutions in electric vehicles. The visit allowed for a firsthand look at the practical applications and advancements achieved through the FLAMINGo Project at Alke Electric Vehicles' premises.

New FLAMINGo flyer released

We're excited to present our newest flyer. The FLAMINGo Project is advancing, and the outcomes are truly remarkable. Dive into the details about our Initial Results, Success Stories, and the far-reaching Impacts. Stay connected for ongoing updates towards the development of lighter and more sustainable EVs. Check it out: https://lnkd.in/ed_GDYWa

Enlight EVs factsheet & video

The FLAMINGo H2020 Project, proudly collaborates with the EnLight EVs cluster, joining forces with fellow projects such as REVOLUTION, LEVIS, Fatigue4Light, and ALMA. Together, we are dedicated to advancing lightweight solutions for electric vehicles, contributing to enhanced energy efficiency.

Find out more by exploring our informative factsheet available [HERE](#).

Don't miss our engaging video following this [link](#).

6. News and Updates

Press Releases

This press release summarises the 26-month meeting of the FLAMINGo consortium that took place in Leoben, 8 - 9 March 2023. The meeting provided a valuable platform for collaborative decision-making, knowledge exchange, and strategic planning, ensuring that FLAMINGo remains on course to fulfil its objectives.

Check out our press release [here](#).

A new press release was released highlighting the EVs Cluster Webinar, a noteworthy event held as part of the EU Green Week activities on June 6, 2023. This webinar marked a significant contribution to the discussions and initiatives surrounding "sustainable mobility through implementing advanced solutions and lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles".

Check out our press release [here](#).

A new press release focusing on the LCA workshop successfully organised by Enligh EVs on February 9th was also announced. FLAMINGo project partner EXELISIS was among the session moderators coordinating the interesting discussions on how to improve products' environmental performance.

Visit our website section [here](#).

The project's 9th Press Release presented the rich insights and key takeaways from our presenters of the recent webinar, 'The Circular Metal for Future Mobility.' This engaging and informative webinar, organized within the framework of the SALEMA EU project, played a pivotal role in advancing discussions around sustainable automotive materials.

Click [here](#) for our Press Release.

6. News and Updates

FLAMINGo featured at EAA Innovation Hub Newsletter

FLAMINGo project was presented at the EAA's Innovation Newsletter, issued by the European Aluminium Innovation Hub. The Innovation Hub serves as an industrial platform committed to enhancing innovation throughout the aluminum value chain via collaborative projects and initiatives. This newsletter provides updates on key activities within the Innovation Hub, along with compelling innovation narratives from its members, and highlights news about associated projects, events, and proposals.

At their 11th Issue, FLAMINGo outline was presented focusing on the project targets, including a 10% reduction in vehicle weight, emphasising applications in electric vehicles to replace steel components. The importance of including Al-MMnCo components for achieving weight savings of 50 to 30% was also on the spotlight, with a particular focus on steering knuckles and rear frames for electric trucks.

Internal Training on Safety by ISQ & Extrusion by Constellium

The Training on Safety to Advanced (Nano)materials in the Workplace, conducted by ISQ with the support of EWF, was a crucial component of the general meeting held at Austrian

Foundry Research Institute on March 8th-9th, 2023.

With the participation of 50 individuals, this training aimed to enhance awareness and understanding of safety measures related to advanced materials, particularly nano-materials, within the workplace. The sessions covered hazards related to NPs, regulatory framework, occupational exposure, safe and sustainable design. An interactive part followed dealing with aspects of consumer exposure and its assessment in the future.

The training not only contributed to the overall safety culture of the workplace but also aligned with the FLAMINGo project's commitment to responsible and secure advancements in materials technology.

Followingly, Constellium conducted a training session with EWF's support sharing essential knowledge to FLAMINGo partners about the Extrusion process of Aluminium Alloys. The training covered key aspects such as an overview of Aluminium Alloys' properties, processing steps, the main parameters influencing material performance, and the effects of specific constraints (flow stresses, temperature ranges, shape complexity) on the overall process.

6. News and Updates

Internal exploitation seminar by AXIA

On October 11, Axia Innovation, our exploitation manager, concluded a highly successful training session on Innovation Management exclusively designed for the consortium. The training, expertly organised by the European Welding Federation (EWF), provided a comprehensive exploration of various aspects within this dynamic field. The sessions covered crucial topics, including the exploitation path, categories of exploitable results, protection by intellectual property rights (IPR), exploitation strategy, exploitation route, commercial and non-commercial routes, exploitation routes closely linked to Technology Readiness Levels (TRL), levels of development, and external and internal analysis. This insightful training proved to be a valuable and enriching experience for all participants, enhancing our collective understanding of effective innovation management.

The training session, facilitated by Axia Innovation, our dedicated exploitation manager, was an illuminating journey into the intricacies of Innovation Management. Held on October 11 and orchestrated by the European Welding Federation (EWF), the session covered a wide range of essential topics. These included detailed discussions on the exploitation path, categories of exploitable results, safeguarding through intellectual property rights (IPR), formulation of an exploitation strategy, identification of commercial and non-commercial routes, alignment of exploitation routes with Technology Readiness Levels (TRL),

understanding levels of development, and conducting external and internal analyses.

This comprehensive training not only broadened our perspectives on effective innovation management but also fostered a collaborative environment for knowledge exchange among the consortium members.

Internal Training on recycling by KAMPAKAS

An additional training conducted by KAMPAKAS on January 8, 2024, focused on the critical aspects of aluminum recycling, provided valuable insights and knowledge to the FLAMINGo consortium. The topics covered during the session included an exploration of the advantages associated with aluminum recycling, emphasising the environmental impact of this sustainable practice. Participants likely gained a comprehensive understanding of scrap selection and the intricate recycling processes involved in transforming discarded aluminum into reusable material.

Quality control emerged as a crucial aspect, ensuring that recycled aluminum meets the required standards and specifications. By delving into the challenges associated with aluminum recycling, the training likely addressed potential hurdles in the process, equipping participants with the necessary information to overcome them.

7. Past Events by Partners

IAB/IIW Meeting, 12 January 2023, (EWF)

On January 12th, the European Welding Federation (EWF) actively participated in the Industry Advisory Board (IAB) meeting, taking the opportunity to showcase and promote the FLAMINGo Project H2020 along with its notable achievements. The IAB meetings play a crucial role in shaping guidelines, rules, and best practices for the global promotion and implementation of the International Institute of Welding's (IIW) Harmonised education, training, qualification, and

certification systems for welding personnel and companies. EWF's presence at this meeting underscores its commitment to contributing to the advancement and dissemination of knowledge in the welding industry, aligning with the overarching mission of the IIW.

This collaborative engagement signifies a concerted effort to enhance standards and practices within the welding community on a global scale.

LCA Webinar 9 February 2023, (EXE, ISWA & AXIA)

Our Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) webinar, a collaborative effort between the FLAMINGo Project H2020 and ALMA Project, took place on February 9th 2023 and was highly successful.

The event was organised and co-hosted by Exelisis, ISWA International Solid Waste Association, and Axia Innovation. We extend our gratitude to the over 80 participants who joined the webinar, contributing to a rich and engaging discussion on Life Cycle Assessment methodologies and techniques. The active participation reflects the collective commitment to advancing knowledge and practices in the field, emphasising sustainability and environmental considerations in the development and lifecycle of automotive components. Stay tuned for more collaborative initiatives and insights from our projects!

Check out more: <https://www.flamingo-project.eu/our-webinar-on-lca-was.../>

7. Past Events by partners

RTR Conference 14 - 16 February 2023, Brussels

The FLAMINGo Project H2020 and our cluster attended the RTR Conference in Brussels from February 14 to 16, 2023. This highly anticipated event was set to attract more than 400 participants, providing a dynamic platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration.

On February 15th, the FLAMINGo project gave a presentation titled "GV - Advanced light materials and their production processes," alongside our EnlightEVs projects. FLAMINGo team had the opportunity to showcase the groundbreaking advancements of the project in advanced light materials and production processes, contributing to the broader discourse on sustainable and innovative solutions in the automotive industry.

Take a look at the agenda: <https://lnkd.in/g28ypS3m>
For more information you may visit: <https://rtrconference.eu/>

TMS 2023 Annual Meeting & Exhibition 19 March 2023, USA (Brunel)

Brunel University participated at the TMS 2023 Annual Meeting & Exhibition held on March 19, 2023, in San Diego, California, USA. With a substantial attendance of over 4000 participants, BUL made significant contributions to the conference through two oral presentations and the publication of two chapters in the conference proceedings of Light Metals 2023.

Beyond the academic aspects, Brunel engaged in extensive networking activities within the relevant communities, fostering connections in the fields of metals and Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs).

For more information about the event, please visit <https://www.tms.org/AnnualMeeting/TMS2023>.

7. Past Events by partners

ECTP 2023 10 - 13 September 2023, Italy (ÖGI)

ÖGI participated in the EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON THERMOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES (ECTP) held in Venice from September 10 to 13, 2023. During the conference, ÖGI engaged in flyer distribution and networking activities, contributing to the dissemination of information related to the FLAMINGo project. The networking opportunities provided a platform for ÖGI to

connect with professionals, researchers, and stakeholders in the field of thermophysical properties. This active participation in the ECTP conference aligns with FLAMINGo's commitment to sharing knowledge and fostering collaborations within the scientific community.

More information about the conference can be found at <https://www.ectp2023.eu/>.

63rd International Foundry Conference 13 - 15 September 2023, Slovenia (ÖGI)

DRUŠTVO LIVARJEV SLOVENIJE
SLOVENIAN FOUNDRYMEN SOCIETY

Član The World Foundry Organization
Member of World Foundry Organization

ÖGI, participated at the 63rd International Foundry Conference (IFC) conducted from September 13 to 15, 2023, in Portoroz. Throughout the event, ÖGI had the chance to distribute informational flyers and engaged in networking initiatives, facilitating the widespread dissemination of valuable insights linked to the FLAMINGo project. ÖGI contributed to raising awareness in the groundbreaking advancements achieved within FLAMINGo, with a specific focus on innovations in foundry technology.

Further information about the conference is available at <https://www.drustvo-livarjev.si/home>.

ÖGI at the 1st Materials Job Fair
15 March 2023, Leoben

Material Job Fair 15 March 2023, Austria (ÖGI)

The Materials Job Fair Leoben, held on March 15th, 2023, in Leoben, provided a platform for various institutes and research facilities to showcase their ongoing projects, scientific theses, and available positions. ÖGI participated in the event, sharing a dedicated booth to

showcase the FLAMINGo Project H2O2O with attendees. This engagement allowed for the dissemination of information about the project and facilitated interactions with individuals interested in the innovative developments within FLAMINGo.

7. Past Events by partners

ACstyria Lightweight Day 2023 1 - 2 March 2023, Austria (ÖGI)

The ACstyria Lightweight Day 2023, hosted at in Spielberg, Austria, from March 1st to 2nd, 2023, featured prominent figures from the industry, science, and research sectors sharing practical strategies for weight reduction in

transportation. ÖGI actively participated in the exhibition, taking the opportunity to showcase and discuss the FLAMINGo Project H2020 during the event.

65th Austrian Foundry Conference 27 - 28 April 2023, Austria (ÖGI)

The 65th Austrian Foundry Conference 2023, held in Schladming, Austria, from April 27th to 28th, provided a valuable platform for ÖGI to showcase the FLAMINGo Project H2020. The conference addressed critical issues in the foundry sector, including economic challenges, climate neutrality, digitalisation, and the transition to e-mobility.

ÖGI at the 65th Austrian Foundry Conference
27-28 April 2023, Leoben

Explore snapshots from the conference and learn more on our website: <https://lnkd.in/ep-7rgWj>.

1st International Conference on Lightweight Materials 11 - 12 May 2023, Italy

The 1st International Conference on Lightweight materials 2023, held at Politecnico di Milano, Italy, on May 11th - 12th, 2023, saw active participation from key representatives of the FLAMINGo Project H2020, including Axia Innovation, Exelisis, ISQ, MBN, Brunel University London, and ÖGI. The conference aimed to foster

industry development by showcasing notable advancements in the materials sector, particularly focusing on lightweight materials. Attendees benefited from a diverse range of technical presentations delivered by experts from academia, industry, and Open Innovation Test Beds, contributing to the collective knowledge in the field.

Find out more: <https://www.flamingo-project.eu/flamingo-at-the-1st.../>.

7. Past Events by partners

Inhaled Particles & NanoDEH Conference 15 - 18 May 2023, UK (ISQ)

ISQ recently showcased the FLAMINGO Project H2020 at the Inhaled Particles and NanoDEH Conference 2023 in Manchester, UK, from the 15th to the 18th of May 2023.

This collaborative conference brought together a diverse group of experts and early career researchers specialising in occupational health and exposure, modeling, epidemiology, and toxicology. The joint symposium aimed to tackle crucial issues within the discipline, share new findings, and discuss the future trajectory of research. Additionally, it provided a platform to assess the appropriateness and viability of various approaches to address pertinent questions in the field.

Find out more on our Website: <https://www.flamingo-project.eu/isq-at-the-inhaled.../>.

EU Green Week 6 June 2023, (ÖGI)

On June 6th, our colleague Tosé Petkov from ÖGI highlighted the FLAMINGO Project H2020 at the EUGreenWeek EnLight EV's Cluster Event.

EU GREEN WEEK
"Towards a more sustainable mobility through the implementation of advanced solutions and lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles"
06 June 2023, online

Thank you for joining us!

Mr. Tosé Petkov
ÖGI

The presentation focused on industry skills required to introduce new materials for sustainable mobility, using aluminum Nano-composites as an example. Representatives from other EnLight EV projects—ALMA, LEVIS, Fatigue4Light, and REVOLUTION—also participated, showcasing their research outcomes aimed at achieving more sustainable mobility through advanced solutions and lightweight materials in Electric Vehicles.

7. Past Events by partners

NanoSAFE 2023 5 - 9 June 2023, France (ISO)

The FLAMINGo Project H2020 made a notable appearance at the NanoSAFE23 & NanoSafety Cluster conference in Grenoble from June 5th to 9th, 2023. ISO, our partner overseeing nano-safety matters, showcased their latest contributions to EU projects during the event.

The emphasis was on advocating for a strategy that prioritises safety and sustainability in the design of processes and products.

IAA Mobility Conference 2023 5 - 10 September 2023, (AXIA)

Axia Innovation, actively engaged in the IAA Mobility Open Space Conference held in Munich from September 5th to 10th. The event provided a valuable platform for connecting with fellow innovators and industry leaders, fostering the exchange of groundbreaking ideas in the mobility sector. Notably, we seized the opportunity to promote our innovative FLAMINGo Project H2020 by distributing informative flyers that outlined the project's vision. The response was overwhelmingly positive, and we appreciate the enthusiastic support received during this remarkable event.

Webinar hosted by SALEMA EU project 6 October 2023, (MBN)

On October 6th 2023, the FLAMINGo Project H2020 was showcased in the webinar: "The Circular Metal for Future Mobility: aluminium for lightweight and sustainability," hosted by the SALEMA EU project. Our coordinator, Alvise Bianchin from MBN, provided a comprehensive

overview of our project, alongside other insightful presentations. The presentation by MBN Nanomaterialia delved into "Circularity, feasibility, and effects of nanoparticle inclusion in aluminium alloys."

8. Future Events by Partners

◆ TRA 2024, 15 - 18 April 2024, Dublin, Ireland

Scheduled for April 15 to 18, 2024, in Dublin, Ireland, the Transport Research Arena (TRA) will be organised. This is a prominent European event in the transportation sector that covers all modes of transport and aspects of mobility. TRA provides a pivotal platform for researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders to participate in discussions on the transformative impact of research and innovation on transportation and mobility.

The conference facilitates a unique opportunity to understand mobility trends in diverse European regions, learn from industry achievements, and share best practices in policies and implementations.

FLAMINGo will be there to present our concept, developments and main expected outcomes during the last year of our project. Find out more: <https://traconference.eu/>

◆ 3D Additive EXPO, 7 - 9 November 2024, Batalha, Portugal

The 3D ADDITIVE EXPO 2024, scheduled to take place from Thursday, November 7, 2024, to Saturday, November 9, 2024, at ExpoSalao in Batalha, Portugal, stands as a notable event in the realm of 3D printing and additive manufacturing.

This exposition is designed to bring together industry experts, innovators, and enthusiasts to explore the latest trends and breakthroughs in additive manufacturing technologies. With a primary focus on 3D printing, the event encompasses a diverse range of applications and solutions.

For FLAMINGo, the 3D ADDITIVE EXPO 2024 could have a valuable opportunity to exhibit and highlight its cutting-edge innovations in lightweight materials and advanced manufacturing processes. By participating in this expo, FLAMINGo can engage with a diverse audience, including professionals, researchers, and potential collaborators.

Find out more: [3D ADDITIVE EXPOSALÃO - 2024 - Evento \(exposalao.pt\)](https://exposalao.pt)

3D ADDITIVE EXPO

8. Future Events by Partners

◆ 77th IIW Annual Assembly & International Conference, 7 - 12 July 2024, Rhodes Island, Greece

The IIW Annual Assembly and International Conference, scheduled to take place from July 7 to July 12, 2024, on Rhodes Island in the Dodecanese, Greece, is a significant global gathering hosted by the Welding Greek Institute. This event is renowned for its comprehensive coverage of the latest advancements in industrial and technical sectors, providing a forum for experts, researchers, and industry professionals to share insights, innovations, and best practices.

For FLAMINGo, the IIW Annual Assembly and International Conference could be a strategic opportunity to showcase its pioneering work in the realms of welding technologies and lightweight materials. Given the Welding Greek Institute's emphasis on welding advancements, FLAMINGo's participation aligns seamlessly with the conference's thematic focus.

Find out more: [IIW 2024 Annual Assembly – Rhodes, 2024 Greece](#)

◆ eMove 360° Europe, 15 - 17 October 2024, München, Germany

The eMove360° Europe 2024 conference, scheduled from October 15 to 17, 2024, at Messe München, presents a targeted opportunity for FLAMINGo to showcase its innovations in the context of charging and energy, battery technology, automated driving, and e-mobility within commercial vehicles. The event's clear focus on these crucial aspects of the electric mobility landscape makes it highly relevant to FLAMINGo's goals in advancing sustainable and lightweight solutions for electric vehicles (EVs).

By participating in eMove360° Europe, FLAMINGo can engage with key stakeholders in the e-mobility sector, including industry leaders, researchers, and policymakers. The conference provides a platform to highlight FLAMINGo's contributions to the development of lightweight materials for EVs, emphasising its role in enhancing energy efficiency, promoting sustainable practices, and contributing to the broader advancements in electric transportation.

Find out more: [eMove360° EUROPE 2024 - eMove360°](#)

9. Contact Info

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The Consortium

FLAMINGo - Fabrication of lightweight aluminium metal matrix nanocomposites and validation in green vehicles

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